

AN ANALYSIS OF THE SOVEREIGN GOLD BOND (SGB) SCHEME IN INDIA: TRENDS AND RETURN PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study analyses the trend, return performance, and investment efficiency of the Sovereign Gold Bond Scheme in comparison with physical gold (0.999 purity). The study is based on secondary data collected from the Reserve Bank of India Bulletins covering the period from 2015–16 to 2023–24. The analysis includes issue price trends, maturity returns, and projected returns of non-matured SGB series using tools such as trend analysis and XIRR.

The findings reveal a consistent upward trend in SGB issue prices, along with superior return performance compared to physical gold due to the combined effect of capital appreciation and fixed interest income. The study also highlights the tax efficiency of SGB, particularly the capital gains tax exemption at maturity, which acts as an added advantage for investors. Overall, the study concludes that SGB is a more attractive and financially efficient investment option than physical gold for long-term investors.

INTRODUCTION

Investment plays a crucial role in an individual's life by enabling the transfer of income into long-term financial security and stable wealth growth (Bodie, Kane, & Marcus, 2021) In the present economic environment, only income generation is not enough to meet future financial needs due to increasing inflation, raising cost of living, and longer life expectancy Investment in instruments such as gold, mutual funds, equities, bonds, real estate, and government securities helps individuals systematically build wealth Regular and disciplined investing allows individuals to benefit from the power of compounding, which enhances wealth build up while protecting purchasing power and ensuring financial stability over time (Reserve Bank of India, 2023) Investment also supports the achievement of important life goals like, education, marriage, housing, healthcare, and retirement planning Further, systematic investment encourages financial discipline, provides tax benefits under prevailing laws, and offers financial protection during emergencies (OECD, 2020) Thus, investment is not merely a financial choice but a necessity for improving living standards and achieving long-term economic security (SEBI, 2022)

INVESTMENT IN GOLD

Among the various investment opportunities, gold remains one of the most preferred and trusted instruments due to its ability to preserve wealth over time (Baur & Lucey, 2010) This preference stems from gold's long-established role as a precious metal and a reliable of value Owing to its rarity, durability, and resistance to corrosion, gold has been widely used in the form of jewellery, coins, and in several industrial and technological applications From an investment perspective, gold serves as an effective hedge against inflation, economic uncertainty, and currency fluctuations, thereby safeguarding investors' purchasing power (Ghosh, Levin, Macmillan, & Wright, 2004) Its high liquidity further enhances its importance by enabling individuals to meet major financial requirements such as education, healthcare, marriage, and retirement planning (World Gold Council, 2021)

Despite these advantages, investment in physical gold is associated with certain limitations that reduce its effectiveness as a financial asset. Issues related to purity verification, risk of theft, storage and insurance costs, and losses arising from making charges and wastage in ornament design adversely affect actual investment returns (Reserve Bank of India, 2022) (SEBI, 2022). In addition, emotional attachment to gold jewellery often discourages timely liquidation during financial emergencies, thereby limiting its practical liquidity. To overcome these limitations, gold bonds have emerged as a safer and more efficient alternative to physical gold.

SOVEREIGN GOLD BOND (SGB)

The Sovereign Gold Bond (SGB) Scheme was launched by the Government of India in November 2015 as part of the broader Gold Monetisation Scheme, with the objective of reducing dependence on physical gold while encouraging financial savings in gold-linked instruments. The bonds are issued by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) on behalf of the Government of India in periodic tranches, the terms and conditions of which are notified by the RBI in consultation with the Government. The issue price of each tranche is announced by the RBI prior to subscription through official press releases (Reserve Bank of India, 2022).

SGBs are available for subscription only to resident Indian entities, including individuals (singly, jointly, or on behalf of a minor), Hindu Undivided Families (HUFs), trusts, universities, and charitable institutions. As per RBI guidelines, submission of a valid Permanent Account Number (PAN) Know Your Customer (KYC) requirements for SGBs are aligned with those applicable to physical gold purchases and include documents such as Aadhaar, PAN, Passport, or Voter ID. The bonds are denominated in grams of gold, with one gram as the basic unit, and the minimum permissible investment is one gram. The maximum subscription limit is capped at four kilograms per financial year for individuals and HUFs, and twenty kilograms for trusts and similar entities, inclusive of subscriptions across all tranches and secondary market purchases (Reserve Bank of India, 2022).

The tenor of Sovereign Gold Bonds is eight years, with an early exit option available after the fifth, sixth, and seventh years on interest payment dates. Investors earn a fixed interest of 25 per cent per annum, payable semi-annually on the nominal value of the bond. An incentive in the form of a discount of ₹50 per gram on the issue price is provided to investors who apply online and make payment through digital modes. Payments for subscription can be made through cash (subject to a maximum limit prescribed by the RBI), cheque, demand draft, or electronic banking channels. Nomination facilities are available except in cases where investments are made on behalf of minors (Reserve Bank of India, 2022). Goyal and Khan (2025) noted that the Sovereign Gold Bond Scheme provides additional financial advantages such as government guarantee, periodic interest income, and capital gains tax exemption at maturity, which indirectly increases the effective return to investors. This tax exemption acts as an “invisible tax benefit” when compared with physical gold investment, where capital gains are taxable upon realization. Investors are provided with holding certificates, with an option to convert the bonds into dematerialised form. The redemption price is determined in Indian rupees based on the simple average of the closing price of gold of 999 purity for the previous three working days, as published by the India Bullion and Jewellers Association (IBJA) (RBI, 2022).

Sovereign Gold Bonds are tradable on recognised stock exchanges within a stipulated period after issuance, subject to RBI notification, and can also be used as collateral for loans. The loan-to-value ratio applicable to SGBs is aligned with that prescribed for ordinary gold loans by the Reserve Bank of India, with lien marking facilitated through authorised banks and depositories. Through these features,

the SGB Scheme offers a secure, transparent, and financially efficient alternative to physical gold, combining price-linked returns with sovereign assurance and additional interest income (SEBI, 2022)

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Gold continues to be a preferred investment instrument due to its role in wealth preservation; however, physical gold investment involves challenges such as storage risk, purity concerns, and limited liquidity during emergencies To address these issues, the Government of India introduced the Sovereign Gold Bond (SGB) Scheme as an alternative to physical gold Although several earlier studies have examined gold as an investment option, limited attention has been given to analysing the Sovereign Gold Bond Scheme with specific focus on trends in issuance and return performance Moreover, empirical evidence on the comparative returns of SGBs and physical gold remains limited In this context, the present study attempts to analyse the trends and return performance of Sovereign Gold Bonds in India using secondary data

Objectives of the Study

1. To understand the conceptual framework of the Sovereign Gold Bond Scheme and the gold market in India
2. To analyse the trends and return performance of Sovereign Gold Bonds in India
3. To compare the return performance of Sovereign Gold Bonds with that of the physical gold market
4. To provide suitable suggestions to investors based on the findings of the study

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study adopts a descriptive and analytical research design and is based exclusively on secondary data The study focuses on analysing trends and return performance of the Sovereign Gold Bond (SGB) Scheme in India Secondary data have been collected primarily from the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) Bulletins, RBI press releases on SGB tranches, and publications of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) Additional supporting information has been obtained from government reports and relevant published studies The period of analysis has been selected based on the availability and consistency of data No primary data have been used in the study

Analysis of the data and interpretation

Table: 1-Trend of SGB Issues and Issue Prices (2015–2024)

Year	Series	SGB price per gram/unit INR. (IP)	issue per in	Issue Date	Year	Series	SGB price per gram/unit INR.(IP)	issue per in	Issue Date
2015-16	I	2684		26/11/2015	2020-21	I	4639		28/04/2020
	II	2600		18/01/2016		II	4590		19/05/2020
	III	2916		29/03/2016		III	4677		16/06/2020
2016-17	I	3119		05/08/2016		IV	4852		14/07/2020

	II	3150	23/09/2016		V	5334	11/08/2020
	III	3007	17/11/2016		VI	5117	08/09/2020
	IV	2943	17/03/2017		VII	5051	20/10/2020
2017-18	I	2951	12/05/2017	2021-22	VIII	5177	18/11/2020
	II	2830	28/07/2017		IX	5000	05/01/2021
	III	2956	16/10/2017		X	5104	19/01/2021
	IV	2987	23/10/2017		XI	4912	09/02/2021
	V	2971	30/10/2017		XII	4662	09/03/2021
	VI	2945	06/11/2017		I	4777	25/05/2021
	VII	2934	13/11/2017		II	4842	01/06/2021
	VIII	2961	20/11/2017		III	4889	08/06/2021
	IX	2964	27/11/2017		IV	4807	20/07/2021
	X	2961	04/12/2017		V	4790	17/08/2021
	XI	2952	11/12/2017		VI	4732	07/09/2021
	XII	2890	18/12/2017		VII	4765	02/11/2021
	XIII	2866	26/12/2017		VIII	4791	07/12/2021
	XIV	2881	01/01/2018		IX	4786	08/01/2022
2018-19	I	3114	04/05/2018	2022-23	X	5109	08/03/2022
	II	3146	23/10/2018		I	5091	28/06/2022
	III	3186	13/11/2018		II	5197	30/08/2022
	IV	3119	01/01/2020		III	5409	27/12/2022
	V	3214	22/01/2020		IV	5611	14/03/2023
	VI	3326	12/02/2020		2023-24	I	5926

2019-20	I	3196	11/06/2010	II	5923	20/09/2023
	II	3443	16/07/2010	III	6199	28/12/2023
	III	3499	14/08/2010	IV	6263	21/02/2024
	IV	3890	17/09/2010			
	V	3788	15/10/2010			
	VI	3835	30/10/2010			
	VII	3795	10/12/2010			
	VIII	4016	21/01/2020			
	IX	4070	11/02/2020			
	X	4260	11/03/2020			

Sources: data computed as per RBI bulletins

Graph1: Trend of SGB Issues and Issue Prices (2015–2024)

Sources: data computed as per RBI bulletins

The issue prices of the Sovereign Gold Bond Scheme from 2015–16 to 2023–24 indicate a clear upward trend over the study period. As shown in Table 1 and Graph 1, the scheme was first issued in November 2015 at a price of ₹2,684 per gram, and since then a total of 67 series of bonds have been

issued through the Reserve Bank of India on behalf of the Government of India. During the initial phase from 2015 to 2017, the issue prices remained relatively stable, fluctuating between ₹2,600 and ₹3,100 per gram. However, during 2018 and 2019, a gradual increase in prices was observed, indicating a steady rise in domestic gold prices. The scheme initially offered an interest rate of 2.75 percent per annum, which was later revised to 2.50 percent per annum, payable semi-annually.

Further, graph 1 clearly depicts both the actual price movement and the linear trend line, which shows a consistent upward slope throughout the study period. A sharp increase in issue prices is visible during 2020, when the price crossed ₹5,000 per gram, largely due to increased demand for gold as a safe investment during global economic uncertainty. Although slight fluctuations were observed in 2021, the overall trend remained positive. From 2022 onwards, the upward movement continued, with prices exceeding ₹6,000 per gram. The highest issue price recorded during the period was ₹6,263 per gram in February 2024, while the lowest price was ₹2,600 per gram in January 2016. Thus, the analysis of Table 1 and graph 1 (including the trend line) confirms a sustained upward trajectory in SGB issue prices, reflecting the increasing value of gold and the growing attractiveness of sovereign gold bonds as a secure financial investment instrument.

Table 2: Actual SGB Maturity Returns and Comparison with Market price of 0.999 purity gold (per gram)

year	series	SGB issue	Maturity price (Physical Gold Price) as maturity date)	Accumulated interest = $IP * R * T$	Total return on SGB = (difference of issue price at maturity and accumulated interest)	Total return on SGB in (Annual) XIRR	Total Return on Physical gold	Total Return on PG in (Annual) XIRR
		IP	MP	AI	RSGB	%SGB	RPG	%PG
2015-16	I	2684	6132	590	4038	12.74	3448	10.88
	II	2600	6263	572	4235	13.74	3663	11.63
	III	2916	6978	642	4704	13.36	4062	11.45
2016-17	I	3119	6938	686	4505	12.39	3819	10.54
	II	3150	7517	693	5060	13.32	4367	11.5
	III	3007	7788	601	5382	14.42	4781	12.73
	IV	2943	8634	589	6280	16.12	5691	14.65
2017-18	I	2951	9486	590	7125	17.38	6535	16.01
	II	2830	9924	566	7660	18.61	7094	17.34
	III	2956	12567	591	10202	21.37	9611	20.39
	IV	2987	12704	597	10314	21.37	9717	20.39
	V	2971	12600	594	10223	21.33	9629	20.36
	VI	2945	12480	589	10124	21.32	9535	20.34
	VII	2934	12350	587	10003	21.32	9416	20.24
	VIII	2961	12420	592	10051	21.17	9459	20.19

IX	2964	12550	593	10179	21.31	9586	20.32
X	2961	12650	592	10281	21.44	9689	20.45
XI	2952	12801	590	10439	21.65	9849	20.07
XII	2890	12700	578	10388	21.85	9810	20.87
XIII	2866	12750	573	10457	22.03	9884	21.05
XIV	2881	12800	576	10495	22.01	9919	21.02

Sources: data computed as per RBI bulletins

Graph 2: Actual SGB Maturity Returns and Comparison with Market price of 0.999 purity gold (per gram)

Sources: data computed as per RBI bulletins

Table 2 and Graph 2 present the actual maturity returns of the Sovereign Gold Bond Scheme and compare them with the returns from 0.999 purity physical gold. The maturity price of SGB is directly linked to the prevailing market price of gold at the time of redemption, which is determined based on the average closing price published by the India Bullion and Jewellers Association and administered through the Reserve Bank of India on behalf of the Government of India. As shown in Table 2 and illustrated in Figure 2, the appreciation in the maturity price of SGB closely follows the increase in the market price of physical gold, indicating that investors benefit from the same price appreciation as physical gold holders.

However, the graphical trend clearly shows that SGB generates higher overall returns compared to physical gold because investors receive both market price appreciation and a fixed interest of 2.5 percent per annum on the initial investment. As reflected in Table 2 and Figure 2, the annual return on SGB ranges approximately from 12.39 percent to 22.03 percent, while the return on physical gold ranges from 10.54 percent to 21.05 percent. The highest return on SGB (about 22.03 percent) was observed in 2017–18 Series XIII, whereas the lowest return (about 12.39 percent) occurred in 2016–17 Series I. In comparison, physical gold provided slightly lower returns because it lacks the additional interest component. Furthermore, SGB offers an important tax advantage. The capital gains arising on redemption for the original investor are exempt from capital gains tax, whereas investors in physical gold must pay capital gains tax when the asset is sold. Although the interest earned on SGB is taxable,

the combination of interest income, market price appreciation, and tax exemption on redemption makes SGB financially stronger than physical gold. Therefore, the analysis of Table 2 and Figure 2 clearly demonstrates that SGB provides higher effective returns and better tax efficiency, making it a more attractive investment instrument compared to physical gold.

Table 3: Projected Growth of SGB Returns and Comparison with Market Price of 999 Purity Gold (Per Gram) for Non-Matured SGB Series

year	series	SGB issue	Time	Market price of gold of 0.999 purity on 310126)	Total return on SGB = (difference of issue price and market price and accumulated interest)	Total return on SGB in (Annual XIRR)	Total Return on Physical gold	Total Return on PG in (Annual XIRR)
2018-19	I	3114	7.74	16026	13515	24.16	12912	23.57
	II	3146	7.27	16026	13452	25.71	12880	25.10
	III	3186	7.22	16026	13415	25.69	12840	25.08
	IV	3119	16.09	16026	14162	11.23	12907	10.71
	V	3214	16.03	16026	14100	11.08	12812	10.54
	VI	3326	15.98	16026	14029	10.89	12700	10.34
2019-20	I	3196	15.65	16026	14081	11.39	12830	10.85
	II	3443	15.56	16026	13922	10.96	12583	10.39
	III	3499	15.48	16026	13881	10.91	12527	10.33
	IV	3890	15.39	16026	13633	10.27	12136	9.64
	V	3788	15.32	16026	13689	10.50	12238	9.87
	VI	3835	15.28	16026	13656	10.44	12191	9.81
	VII	3795	15.17	16026	13670	10.59	12231	9.96
	VIII	4016	6.06	16026	12619	26.43	12010	25.66
	IX	4070	6.01	16026	12567	26.40	11956	25.61
	X	4260	5.93	16026	12397	25.85	11766	25.04
2020-21	I	4639	5.80	16026	12060	24.71	11387	23.83
	II	4590	5.74	16026	12095	25.21	11436	24.34
	III	4677	5.67	16026	12012	25.15	11349	24.26
	IV	4852	5.60	16026	11853	24.70	11174	23.78
	V	5334	5.53	16026	11429	23.01	10692	22.01
	VI	5117	5.45	16026	11607	24.27	10909	23.30
	VII	5051	5.34	16026	11649	25.10	10975	24.14
	VIII	5177	5.26	16026	11530	24.95	10849	23.96
	IX	5000	5.14	16026	11668	26.40	11026	25.43
	X	5104	5.10	16026	11573	26.13	10922	25.15
	XI	4912	5.05	16026	11734	27.34	11114	26.39
	XII	4662	4.97	16026	11943	29.12	11364	28.20
2021-22	I	4777	4.76	16026	11817	29.90	11249	28.95
	II	4842	4.75	16026	11759	29.61	11184	28.66
	III	4889	4.73	16026	11716	29.50	11137	28.53

	IV	4807	4.62	16026	11774	30.74	11219	29.78
	V	4790	4.55	16026	11781	31.36	11236	30.40
	VI	4732	4.49	16026	11826	32.18	11294	31.22
	VII	4765	4.34	16026	11779	33.22	11261	32.24
	VIII	4791	4.25	16026	11744	33.84	11235	32.86
	IX	4786	4.17	16026	11739	34.60	11240	33.62
	X	5109	4.00	16026	11428	34.13	10917	33.08
2022-23	I	5091	3.70	16026	11406	37.40	10935	36.33
	II	5197	3.53	16026	11288	38.68	10829	37.58
	III	5409	3.21	16026	11051	41.44	10617	40.27
	IV	5611	3.00	16026	10835	43.11	10415	41.88
2023-24	I	5926	2.71	16026	10502	45.68	10100	44.36
	II	5923	2.49	16026	10471	50.51	10103	49.14
	III	6199	2.22	16026	10171	54.87	9827	53.40
	IV	6263	2.07	16026	10087	58.97	9763	57.44

Sources: data computed as per RBI bulletins

Graph 3: Projected Growth of SGB Returns and Comparison with Market Price of 999 Purity Gold (Per Gram) for Non-Matured SGB Series

Sources: data computed as per RBI bulletins

Table 3 and Figure 3 present the projected growth of returns for the non-matured series of the Sovereign Gold Bond Scheme by comparing their issue prices with the prevailing market price of 999 purity gold as on 31-01-2026. The market price considered for the analysis is ₹16,026 per gram, which represents the benchmark price for evaluating the appreciation in investment value. The data indicates that the value of SGB investments has increased substantially due to the sharp rise in gold prices over time. As shown in Table 3 and Figure 3, the total return on SGB includes both capital appreciation (difference between issue price and current market price) and accumulated interest income, whereas physical gold investors benefit only from price appreciation.

The analysis clearly shows that the returns from SGB are consistently higher than those from physical gold, mainly because of the additional interest component. For example, in the 2018–19 series, the annual return on SGB ranges around 24–26 percent, compared to 23–25 percent for physical gold. Similarly, the 2020–21 and 2021–22 series show strong annual returns ranging from 24 percent to 34 percent, while the corresponding returns from physical gold remain slightly lower. The highest projected annual return of about 58.97 percent is observed in the 2023–24 Series IV, while the lowest return of about 10.27 percent appears in the 2019–20 Series IV. The graphical representation in Figure 3 also demonstrates that the SGB return curve remains consistently above the physical gold return curve, highlighting the superior performance of SGB investments.

Findings of the Study

1. The Sovereign Gold Bond Scheme shows a consistent upward trend in issue prices from ₹2,684 in 2015 to ₹6,263 in 2024, indicating a strong long-term increase in gold value, as supported by the positive slope of the trend line in Graph 1.
2. A total of 67 SGB series were issued during the study period, reflecting increasing government efforts to promote financial gold as an alternative to physical gold investment.
3. The return performance of SGB is consistently higher than physical gold, as SGB investors earn both capital appreciation and fixed interest (2.50% p.a.), whereas physical gold provides only price appreciation.
4. The highest return on SGB (22.03% annual XIRR) was observed in 2017–18 Series XIII, while the lowest was around 12.39%, but still higher than corresponding physical gold returns, proving the superior performance of SGB.
5. The projected analysis of non-matured bonds shows that SGB continues to outperform physical gold, with returns reaching up to 58.97% annually, supported by rising gold prices and accumulated interest benefits.
6. SGB provides an “invisible tax benefit” through capital gains tax exemption at maturity for original investors, making it more tax-efficient compared to physical gold, where capital gains tax is applicable.

SUGGESTIONS TO INVESTORS

Based on the study, investors seeking long-term exposure to gold should prefer Sovereign Gold Bonds over physical gold due to their higher return potential and additional interest income. SGBs are particularly suitable for risk-averse investors, as they are backed by the Government of India and offer protection against inflation and market uncertainty. Investors are advised to hold SGBs until maturity to maximise benefits arising from interest income and capital gains tax exemption. Further, including SGBs in an investment portfolio can improve diversification while avoiding the storage, security, and purity-related issues associated with physical gold. Overall, SGBs emerge as a superior and financially efficient alternative for long-term gold investment.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Sovereign Gold Bonds are a superior alternative to physical gold, offering higher returns through both capital appreciation and fixed interest income. The upward trend in issue prices and growing investment volumes reflect increasing investor confidence in the scheme. By eliminating storage, security, and purity-related concerns, SGBs enhance investment efficiency. Overall, SGBs emerge as a safe and effective long-term gold investment instrument.

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